

Comparative Evaluation of Pulse Width Modulation Strategies For Hybrid Multilevel Inverter for Application in Photovoltaic Power Extraction

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Abstract: In this paper presents a performance study of multiple references and multiple carrier pulse width modulation (PWM) techniques for HMLI for application in photovoltaic (PV) power extraction. So as to decrease the input current ripples and conjointly to convert high current, low voltage input into a low current output and high voltage output, a two phase interleaved boost converter (IBC) is used between the PV and also the HMLI. The proposed system is created and simulated using MATLAB/Simulink toolbox. In order to verify the effectiveness of the proposed modulation strategies, the following performance parameter is taken for analysis such as power loss, total harmonic distortion, weighted total harmonic distortion, distortion factor and harmonic spread factor and also proposed method is compared with triple reference with inverted sine carrier PWM, triple reference with single triangle carrier PWM and triple triangle carrier with single sine reference PWM. Hardware implementation results are presented for the proposed triple inverted sine carrier with single sine reference PWM controlled inverter configuration.

Key words: Multilevel inverter • Total harmonic distortion • Switching loss • Pulse width modulation

INTRODUCTION

A distributed energy supply consisting of a PV arrays usually needs a high power boost converter for energy management to assist the slow responding PV cell. Photovoltaic cell has advantages over conventional power generation in terms of high power density, quick response and zero emission. In this paper, a two phase interleaved boost converter (IBC) used between photovoltaic array and the hybrid multilevel inverter (HMLI) to decrease the input current ripples and also the steady-state voltage ripples at the output of IBC are reduced.

The HMLI topology has advantages over typical inverters in terms of element count and circuit complexity [1-2]. Fig.1 shows the diagram of seven levels HMLI topology is connected with PV array via a two-phase interleaved boost converter. HMLI topology is created using typical full bridge inverter with associate auxiliary circuit comprising of diodes and IGBT switch. In this paper, Single reference with multiple carriers PWM

and multiple references with single carrier PWM technique is taken for analysis of the system. The performance of HMLI using different modulation methods have been assessed based on Total harmonic distortion, weighted total harmonic distortion, distortion factor, harmonic spread factor and switching loss using Matlab/Simulink. To test the proposed hybrid multilevel inverter configuration, Simulation and experimental results are analyzed and presented.

Hybrid Multilevel Inverter: The single-phase seven-level HMLI consists of the conventional full bridge inverter, three capacitor act as voltage divider and two bidirectional switches and it is shown in Fig. 1. When compared with conventional multilevel inverter and it have following advantages such as reduced number of power diode, power switches and reduced number of capacitor for inverters of an equal number of levels. Proper switching of the inverter will produce seven output voltage levels. The HMLI operations are often separated into seven switching conditions, as shown in Table 1.

Fig. 1: Seven level HMLI topology connected with PV array via a two-phase interleaved boost converter

Table 1: Switching pattern for HMLI

	V_{dc}	$2 V_{dc}/3$	$V_{dc}/3$	0	$-V_{dc}$	$-2 V_{dc}/3$	$-V_{dc}/3$
S1	*1	0	0	1	0	0	0
S2	#0	0	0	1	1	1	1
S3	0	0	0	1	0	0	1
S4	1	1	1	1	0	0	0
S5	0	1	0	0	1	0	0
s6	0	0	1	0	0	1	0

*1= on and #0=off

Pulse Width Modulation Strategies for Seven Level HMLI:

In this work, a new modulation strategy is proposed to generate PWM gating signals for seven levels HMLI. The triple carrier waveform is compared with single reference signal to generate PWM gating signals and additionally single reference waveform is compared with triple carrier waveform to generate PWM gating signal for seven levels HMLI.

Multiple Carrier PWM Technique: A new modulation technique was proposed to generate PWM gating signals in [7]. Multiple inverted sine carriers with sinusoidal

reference PWM (MCISPWM) technique uses the standard sinusoidal reference signal associated an inverted sinusoidal carrier. The control method utilizes the same reference (synchronized sinusoidal signal) because the standard SPWM whereas the carrier triangle signal is a modified one. The control method utilizes associate inverted (high frequency) sinusoidal carrier signal to maximize the output voltage for a given modulation index. Fig. 2 shows the pulse generation pattern for HMLI. Triple inverted sinusoidal carrier waveform are compared with single sinusoidal reference waveform (MCISPWM), the carrier wave form have the equal amplitude and frequency.

Fig. 2: Switching pattern for MCISPWM (triple inverted sine carrier with single sine reference PWM)

Generate the switching pulse; each carrier waveform is compared with the reference waveform. The amplitude of carrier waveform 1 is cross the amplitude of the reference waveform, carrier waveform 2 is compared with a reference waveform till it is cross the amplitude of reference waveform then, carrier waveform 3 is compared with a reference waveform to the amplitude of reference waveform reached zero. Fig. 2 shows the switching pattern for triple inverted sine carrier with single sine reference PWM. The operating frequency of the Switches S1, S3, S5 and S6 are equal to frequency of carrier waveform. Operating frequency of S2 and S4 is equal to fundamental power frequency.

In [8, 9], to obtain the switch pattern, triangular carrier signals (four offset shifted signal) were compared with single sinusoidal wave reference signal (MCSPWM), the triangular carrier signals have the same frequency and amplitude. In the gating pulse generation of the proposed MCSPWM scheme, the inverted sine

carrier waveform of MCISPWM is replaced by a triangular carrier waveform. Fig. 3 shows the carrier and reference waveform of MCSPWM technique.

Multiple Reference PWM Technique: Multiple references with inverted sine carrier PWM (MRISPWM) technique uses the standard sinusoidal reference signal associated an inverted sine carrier. The control strategy uses the same reference (synchronized sinusoidal signal) because the standard SPWM whereas the carrier triangle is a modified one. The control scheme uses associate inverted (high frequency) sinusoidal carrier signal to maximize the output voltage for a given modulation index. In Fig. 4 shows the pulse generation circuit for HMLI. The triple reference waveforms have equal amplitude and frequency and in phase with a offset value that is equal to the amplitude of the carrier waveform. Each reference waveform is compared with the carrier waveform to generate the pulse width modulation switching logic pulse.

Fig. 3: Carrier and reference waveform for MCSPWM (triple triangle carrier with single sine reference PWM)

Fig. 4: Switching pattern for MRISPWM technique (triple reference with inverted sine carrier PWM)

Fig. 5: Carrier and reference waveform for MRTPWM (triple reference with single triangle carrier PWM)

The reference waveform amplitude is cross the peak amplitude of carrier waveform, reference waveform 2 is compared with carrier waveform till it is cross the peak amplitude of carrier waveform. Then, reference waveform 3 is compared with carrier waveform till it become zero. Once reference waveform 3 is become zero, reference waveform 2 is compared till it become zero. Then, onward, reference waveform 1 is compared with carrier waveform. Fig. 4 shows the pulse width modulated pulse. The operating frequency of switches S6, S5, S3 and S1 are equal to carrier waveform frequency; whereas frequency of S4 and S2 are equal to reference waveform frequency. Modulation index (Ma) of the hybrid seven-level inverter is described in equation (1),

$$M_a = \frac{V_m}{3 * V_c} \tag{1}$$

where, V_m is the peak amplitude of the reference waveform and V_c is the peak to peak magnitude of the carrier waveform. Because, in this paper, reference waveforms have equal magnitude and frequency, equation (1) is articulated in terms of the magnitude of reference waveform ($V_m=V_{ref1}=V_{ref2}=V_{ref3}$) and carrier waveform (V_c).

Similarly, triple reference waveform [2] is compared with single triangle carrier waveform (MRTPWM). The triple reference waveforms have equal amplitude and frequency and in phase with an offset value that is equal to the magnitude of the carrier waveform. Pulse width modulated switching pattern is generated by comparing reference waveforms with carrier waveform. Fig. 5 depicts the waveform of carrier and reference waveform used in MRTPWM technique.

Simulation Results: PV array is modeled using MATLAB/simulink toolbox for the considered parameter of the PV panel such as cathode pressure is 1 bar, anode pressure is 1.5 bar and temperature of the cell is 323 K. Fig. 6 shows the P-V and I-V characteristics of considered PV array with various irradiance level.

Low voltage, high current input from the PV array is converted into a high voltage, low current output using IBC [10, 11]. The interleaved boost converter has advantages over the classical boost converter are high efficiency, low input current ripple, faster response, reduced electromagnetic emission and improved reliability. The high efficiency is gained by separating the output current into ‘n’ paths [12], considerably reducing inductor loss and I^2R losses. Fig. 7 shows the gating pulses for switches of the two phases of the IBC and it is shifted by 180 degrees. The input current, inductor current and output voltage ripple are shown in Fig. 8. The IBC output voltage waveform is shown in Fig. 9.

The simulation results of IBC are compared thereto of a PV array connected to a standard boost converter that is shown in Table 3. The interleaved boost converter provides low input current ripple, high efficiency, quicker transient response, low output voltage ripple.

The MATLAB/Simulink toolbox is used to simulate the different modulation strategies for HMLI with the parameters shown in Table 4. For reasonable comparisons, five performance parameters are taken for analysis that are, power loss, total harmonic distortion, weighted total harmonic distortion, distortion factor and harmonic spread factor. These parameters are obtained for different modulation index and it is shown in Table 5. From the Table 5, all parameters are only favor for triple inverted sine carrier with single sine reference PWM.

Fig. 6: P-V and I-V characteristics of Photovoltaic array

Fig. 7: Gating pulses for 2-phase IBC

Fig. 8: 2-phase IBC inductor current ripple, input current ripple and output voltage ripple

Fig. 9: 2-phase IBC output voltage

Table 2: Simulation parameters for 2-phase IBC

PV open circuit voltage V_{oc}	36.3 Volts
Boost Converter output voltage V_o	100 Volts
Voltage at Load terminal V_1	100 Volts
Switching frequency F_s	20 kHz
L	500 μ H
C	1000 μ F
Duty ratio	0.5

Table 3: Performance characteristics of IBC and classical boost converter

Parameter	Classical Boost converter	IBC
Current ripple (Input)	1.76%	0.08%
Voltage ripple (output)	13.8%	7.36%
Inductor current ripple	0.87%	0.04%

Table 4: Simulation parameters for HMLI

Input voltage	100 V
Switching frequency F_s	3150Hz
C1, C2, C3	1000uF
R	10 Ω
L	3 mH
Modulation index	0.1-0.9

Table 5: Comparison of modulation strategies

Modulation strategies	Total Harmonic Distortion Modulation index				
	0.1	0.3	0.5	0.7	0.9
A	16.24	14.38	7.08	6.32	3.71
B	16.88	14.61	7.13	6.35	3.87
C	16.21	13.13	7.089	6.14	3.59
D	16.76	14.29	8.09	6.93	4.70
Modulation strategies	Weighted Total Harmonic Distortion Modulation index				
	0.1	0.3	0.5	0.7	0.9
A	4.93	4.39	1.57	1.44	0.85
B	5.16	4.43	1.56	1.45	0.86
C	1.95	1.91	1.20	0.78	0.39
D	9.92	3.95	2.35	1.36	1.14

Table 5: Continued

Modulation strategies	Distortion Factor Modulation index				
	0.1	0.3	0.5	0.7	0.9
A	1.64	1.51	0.54	0.44	0.30
B	1.74	1.51	0.528017	0.43	0.29
C	0.96	0.95	0.57	0.34	0.12
D	3.18	1.56	0.87	0.30	0.33
Modulation strategies	Harmonic Spread Factor Modulation index				
	0.1	0.3	0.5	0.7	0.9
A	2.13	3.49	2.62	2.80	2.12
B	2.21	3.51	2.61	2.86	2.22
C	0.30	0.94	1.01	0.93	0.91
D	1.60	2.50	3.57	4.03	2.45

- A-triple reference with inverted sine carrier PWM
- B-triple reference with single triangle carrier PWM
- C-triple inverted sine carrier with single sine reference PWM
- D-triple triangle carrier with single sine reference PWM

In this paper the process of calculating the IGBT power losses using PSIM thermal module is described. Fig. 10 shows the completed HMLI circuit using IGBT thermal module. The gate pulse for IGBT is obtained from Matlab/Simulink via simcoupler. The modulation index, switching frequency, load resistance and load inductance are selected such that the circuit operates under specified condition. Each IGBT module consists of one gating signal node on the left side and four extra nodes on the right side. These four nodes for the power losses and they are (from top to bottom) IGBT conduction losses, IGBT switching losses, diode conduction losses and diode switching losses respectively. They are in the form of electric current and will flow out of these nodes. To measure the power losses value connect an ammeter to each nodes. Table 6 shows the total loss values for different modulation strategies.

Fig. 10: Power loss calculation using PSIM

Table 6: Comparison of power loss

Modulation strategies	Switch s_1, s_3 (mJ)	Switch s_2, s_4 (mJ)	Switch s_5, s_6 (mJ)	Total losses (mJ)
A	13.75	31.54	18.52	127.62
C	15.78	32.82	18.15	133.5
C	10.56	29.99	20.16	121.42
D	19.62	34.87	16.36	141.69

Fig. 11: Output voltage and current waveform of MCISPWM based HMLI switching technique

From Table 5 and Table 6, multicarrier inverted sine PWM (MCISPWM) provides lower THD; lower switching loss and high RMS output voltage value. Fig. 11 shows inverter voltage and inverter current waveforms for triple inverted sine carrier with single

sine reference PWM based HMLI for power extraction in PV array using IBC. The inverter voltage THD measurement of triple inverted sine carrier with single sine reference PWM based HMLI is shown in Fig. 12.

Fig. 12: THD of MCISPWM based HMLI switching technique

Fig. 13: Experimental setup for the prototype single-phase seven-level MCISPWM inverter

Fig. 14: Gate pulse for S1 and S2

Fig. 15: Gate pulse for S3 and S4

Fig. 16: Gate pulse for S5 and S6

Fig. 17: Experimental results of the output voltage of MCISPWM based hybrid HMLI

Experimental Results: A prototype of a seven-level hybrid multilevel inverter (Single Phase) has been designed in order to verify the simulation results. Fig. 13 shows the prototype of the seven-level MCISPWM based hybrid multilevel inverter. By comparing the three carrier signals with the single reference signal in the SPARTAN- 3A FPGA board for pulse generation. The main power circuit consists of two phase interleaved boost converter and 2 SPM IGBT model (FSBB20CH60B). The Optocoupler 6N137 is used to isolate the power circuit from the FPGA circuit, Figs. 14-16 shows the gating pattern of switches (S1-S6). Fig. 17 shows the experimental result for output voltages of hybrid HMLI.

CONCLUSION

The simulation and hardware implementation of seven level hybrid multi level inverter is presented. The proposed multi level inverter has less number of switches than a conventional multilevel inverter. By analysis the results, THD is reduced in the proposed inverter over conventional MLI. A two phase interleaved boost converter has been designed and analyzed for converting the low voltage, high current output from PV array into high voltage, low current output. It is ascertained that interleaved boost converter effectively reduces the current ripple in input side over the conventional boost

converter. This paper also presented a different pulse width modulation switching strategy for the proposed multilevel inverter. It uses; multiple carrier signal and multiple reference signal PWM techniques for generate gating pulse signals to HMLI. A comparative study of different modulation strategies for HMLI has been analyzed, it is found that the multicarrier inverted sine PWM (MCISPWM) provides lower THD, lower switching loss and high RMS output voltage value. Therefore, the proposed HMLI with MCISPWM switching technique is a suitable topology for PV array power extraction.

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